

THE BASIS FOR THE CREATION OF A LEGAL SYSTEM OF HUMAN RIGHTS AND GENDER EQUALITY, ITS PLACE IN INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL LAW. MECHANISM FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The scope of the conditions created for the implementation of the mechanism of protection of gender equality on an international and regional basis, the solution of the problems of employment, the essence of the reforms in this area.

The processes of globalization and integration at the international level contribute to the growth of economic ties between the peoples of the world, the development of urbanization, changes in the social, political, cultural and spiritual environment, primarily due to human capital. The gradual development of the human factor, which has led to its recognition as a century, the centuries-old revolutionary changes, the struggle for human rights and freedoms are resolved peacefully, not by armed uprisings. Historical processes have shown that feudalism was a bloody struggle for power in the era of slavery, a brutal violation of human rights, a brutal oppression of them "history of the savage ancient world" although it has given way to the uneducated and harmonious Middle Ages, it has grown. Even in the developed countries of advanced Europe, the concept of human

rights was applied only to the nobility, the interests of the oppressed people were ignored, they became depressed, the idea of human rights in human society as an independent subject of law. It is clear that the first appearance of law in a first-class society led to the creation of an imperfect legal system that did not define the concepts of man, rights and freedoms. The idea of equality of rights is relatively evolving, which laid the foundation for the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the international legal system. It has a distant native space".

As society has evolved, the issue of human rights and gender equality has become a gap in jurisprudence.

Widespread protests against feudalism helped to spread progressive ideas among the intelligentsia and to attract them to the general public. By the Renaissance, human rights had become a major public concern.

During this period, humanist leaders such as John Locke, Denis Diderot, Charles Montesquieu, Spinoza, and Geotsky advocated the innate rights and equality of the people. With the rise of industrial civilization and the rise of political elites, the demand for the working class increased as the economy entered a period of industrialization. adopted legal documents strengthening their rights.

The first universal recognition of human rights is the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations on December 10, 1948, as noted above. Each paragraph of this 30-article international legal document sets out the priorities for the protection of human freedom, equality, honor and dignity. The declaration not only strengthened the mechanism for the implementation of human rights, but also raised the prelude to changes in the field of human rights to a new level.

It is no exaggeration to say that the protection of the rights of women and men as an integral part of human rights and the prevention of all forms of discrimination against them are causing great concern to the world community in the 21st century. Eliminate all forms of discrimination against women at the national, regional and international levels in political and social life, as well as gender, make them a leading force in public administration and create a sense of involvement in governance. it should be noted that the creation of equal legal opportunities and privileges in life is the primary task of society. If our state continues to pursue an equal, fair state policy towards women and men, to find its place in society and, of course, to create a healthy environment for women in the family, to prevent all forms of oppression and violence against them , remains the

most important and sensitive issue in the legislative system.

The scale created in the implementation of the mechanism for the protection of human rights and gender equality on an international and regional basis and the solutions to the existing problems are full of our national identity and mentality based on world experience. the foundations of the corresponding eastern legal system were laid from the time of the Timurids to the time of the khanates.

A brief look at our long history shows that while the Soviet-era policy of "Assault" saved women and women from ignorance under the veil of innocence, in many areas innocent women became victims of their loved ones. it is worth mentioning. During this period, ordinary Oriental women became victims of politics in the brutal savagery that resulted from the complete absence of the notion of "freedom, liberty" in dependence under the influence of religious bigotry and a mixture of Eastern customary norms. The main reason for this is that the indigenous people of the country do not understand the essence of the policy pursued, religious ignorance has become an integral part of everyday life, and most importantly, it is the wrong policy of the Soviet government. At a time when the people of the country were not yet ready for the policy of aggression, such brutal bloodshed against women would not have taken place if women were given their rights step by step instead of mass liberation. Such sacrifices are a small mistake of great history.

In his speech at the joint session of the Oliy Majlis on December 5, 1998, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov said: determined. To us, this value

is more valuable. Because we treat women with respect from the East. ”

Addressing the plenary session of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on June 21, 2019, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: “Since ancient times, our people have shown great respect for women, especially the image of the holy mother. Respect for women is, first of all, respect for the family, for the future of our

society. From this point of view, the cultural level of any society is determined by its attitude towards women.” On September 2, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men” enshrines women's personal, political, social and other rights. were guarantees of economic rights

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